

SMART CLOUD WITH DOCUMENT CLUSTERING

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Abstract:

This research paper describes the results oriented from experimental study of conventional document clustering techniques implemented in the commercial spaces so far. Particularly, we compared main approaches related to document clustering, agglomerative hierarchical clustering and K-means. though this paper, we generates and implement checker's algorithms which deals with the duplicacy of the document content with the rest of the documents in the cloud. We also generate algorithm required to deals with the classification of the cloud data. The classification in this algorithm is done on the basis of the date of data uploaded and the how much that data is accessed by the client. We will take the ratio of both vectors and generate a score which rates the document in the classification. We propose an explanation for these results that is based on an analysis of the specifics of the clustering algorithms and the nature of document data.

Keywords: algorithm, commercial, classification, hierarchical, nature, etc.

1) Introduction

Most of the devices now-a-days used the cloud platform to store their data. The devices are running on the cloud. Many of the applications are running on the cloud. Cloud contains a lot of identical data in it. While user search for a file in the cloud, these identical files will make a huge problem in doing searching. The files are not classified in the cloud such that it can make easier to the user to search for a desired file. This will affect the efficiency of the cloud. The network cost is also high while accessing the cloud because the data is not transmitted from your neighbourhood, it is from miles of distance from a server on which it resides. This miles of distance may also effect the efficiency in accessing the cloud service. There are a lot more errors in accessing the data at a distance server. These all are the issues in today's cloud service.

We considering ‘TEXT’ type of data to make the cloud to do smarter operations on the server side and make the services more efficient. For that we use to process the document when the user wants it to upload it to the cloud, before uploading, the server process the content of the document and matches the content with the uploaded content in cloud, if there is more than X%(value depends on user) of content matches with the previously uploaded document, the cloud generates a warning to the user. It depends on the server, what type of restrictions it provides to user to upload identical document or not. As the document content not matched with the previous uploads, then document is uploaded on the cloud. This process is used to not allow the duplicate content in the cloud. The second operation is to classify the data in such a manner that user finds it desired document on cloud. For that we classify the documents in a ratio of their upload days and accessing users. This helps the user to get the most popular and the most trending documents with respect to time. The classification of the documents depends on both the scenarios, 1. How much the document is old? 2. How many users accessed that document till moment? The document with the highest score is on the top of the search. This operation allows user to enhance the search in the cloud. The third operation is run when user wants to access any document from the cloud. This operation uses the location of user and finds the nearest server from the user’s location and give an option to the user to access the document with the nearest server location. This can enhance the more accuracy in accessing the document may help the cloud to become smart. Further, there are algorithms to describe how to proceed these operations of cloud and makes the smart cloud.

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are various techniques and algorithms present to enhancing the performance of the cloud. Enhancing the security of cloud data by applying 3d security, in this there is a framework which is divided in two phase. 1st phase contribute in doing encryption of data and classify it before storing. It can be classified into three parameters namely confidentiality, integrity, availability. The parameters measures the critical rating and protection ring is given to data on the bases of critical rating. In the 2nd phase, the user who want to access the data need to authenticate.

A private cloud file management system which is able to do automatic clustering of files and enhance the document management in cloud. The system propose a hybrid algorithm based on top-k frequent itemsets and k-means. The top-k frequent itemsets of the SHDC algorithms found the utilization parTFI algorithm. Documentation set, which incorporates all parts of a common set of terms, been observed as a cluster candidates and their mean value as the initial k-means cluster seed polymerization similar file the clustering by the k-means on the basis of set of term of the top k frequent to accomplishing initial cluster returns.

Solving the problem on big data classification of network intrusion traffic by combining supervised learning techniques, representation-learning techniques, machine lifelong learning techniques and big data technologies. It suggested a combination of modern technologies, Hadoop Distributed File Systems and Cloud Technologies, with the most recent representation-learning technique and support vector machine to predict network intrusions through Big Data classification methodology

Classify encrypted data by k-NN classifier. The protocol protects the confidentiality of the data, user's input query, and hides the data access patterns.

Enhancing text clustering by genetic algorithm. The strategy comprises of Phase 1 and Phase 2 where the Phase 1 is clustering the sentences based on modified repeated spectral bisection. Here an initial clustering is done based on the sign of elements of the Eigen vectors of the similarity matrix. Phase 2 is clustering sentences based on the genetic algorithm, where chromosomes are made.

Enhancing the security of files in cloud by classify them into sensitive and non-sensitive data with the help of k-NN classifier and then using RSA encryption on sensitive data stored them in separately irrespective of non-sensitive data. This classification is based on the confidentiality.

II. PROBLEM STATED

The cloud services are openly available for all kinds of organization and the users. The first problem is that cloud contains a lot of files or data so there is a duplicacy problem happens in

cloud data. Because of no. of files, the content of file can be same as the file already present in the cloud and client upload the file with different name and this is the cause of duplicacy in content on cloud.

NO.	NAME	SIZE(KB)
1.	Security.pdf	253
2.	Networking.doc	1,208
3.	Pin_codes.pdf	452
4.	Advance_networking.pdf	178
5.	Design_issues.doc	2,183
6.	Codes.doc	452
7.	Information storage and management.txt	915

Table 1 (list of files on cloud)

As we noticed that ‘Networking.doc’ and ‘Advance_networking.pdf ’ content is same and ‘Pin_codes.pdf ’ and ‘Codes.doc’ content is also same but both duplicate content files are uploaded to cloud with different names.

$$\text{Total Size} = 253 + 178 + 452 + 178 + 213 + 452 + 412 = 2,138 \text{ KB's}$$

When we analysis the cloud data, there are a many of the files detect which has the same content that's the problem.

Now, there are a lot of files in the cloud and the clients which uses the cloud service got confused to search the file he wants to access. We search for a word and documents related to the word are listed as follows:

In **table 2**, **download** specifies **number of files downloaded** by clients and **Days** specifies for **how many days the file** would be on cloud.

The documents in the list are in the unclassified manner and it is difficult for the client to search the desire document he want which is again a problem for the client.

ID	File	Download	Days
1	3D Security	40	6
2	A Private Cloud Document Management System with Document Clustering Algorithm	69	8
3	Big Data Classification Problems and Challenges	52	7
4	Classification Of Big Point Cloud Data Using Cloud Computing	78	5
5	Classification of Cloud Data using Bayesian	130	9
6	Classification of Gene Expression Data on Public Clouds	89	8
7	Cloud Classification for Weather Information	150	13
8	Data Classification Based on Confidentiality in Virtual Cloud Environment	452	20
9	Implementation of Text clustering using Genetic	230	45
10	k-Nearest Neighbour Classification over Semantically Secure Encrypted Cloud Data	521	54
11	Performance Enhancement of Classifiers using Integration of Clustering and Classification Techniques	632	45
12	Plagiarism Detection Based on SCAM Algorithm	745	98
13	Web Document Clustering Approaches Using K-Means Algorithm	456	75

Table 2 (Files contains user searched word)

The third problem is how efficient the cloud services are, while client accessing files.

ID	Server	Latitude	Longitude	Distance from Noida(Km)
1	Australia	-25.837	130.2848	8439.54
2	Algeria	28.1731	2.5908	8311.058
3	Germany	52.1786	10.2694	7906.55
4	Brazil	-9.019	-53.7216	15159.13
5	China	35.3789	104.3335	3096.395
6	Canada	59.5369	-112.2685	21361.85
7	U.S	41.5811	-100.3329	19808.08
8	Mexico	24.5375	-102.364	19985.81
9	Russia	66.1844	105.4268	5221.908
10	Korea	35.2743	127.6527	5644.406

Table 3 (Server distance with Noida)

The file is available on these servers, but cloud service randomly gives any server to client to access. When it gives Canada server to access the file in place of any nearby server available, the efficiency of network decreases, which is again a big problem.

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

Content Duplicacy Checker using text Summarization:

In this paper, we generates checker's algorithms which deals with the duplicacy of the document content with the rest of the documents in the cloud. The algorithm deals with the process of text summarization of document with the help of following steps:

- 1. Tokenization:** It is the process of removing the white spaces from the document. The whitespaces characters such as spaces, punctuations, line break. The process can removes these tokens and results document further goes for stemming.
- 2. Stemming:** In this process, there are wordnet library which is used to find the stem of the word and consider that stem of word as the word itself.

Example: There are two word 'playing' and 'play', stemming would identify the two words as the word 'playing' is the stem of the word 'play' and treat both words as same.

- 3. Removal of stop word:** There are various stop words in the document which we can't compare, so we have to remove those also to make a genuine content compare document. The most common stop words are such as **the, is, at, which, on** and so on. After removing these, the remaining data is saved to the database for comparing purpose.

Algorithm:

Variables	Description
D	Set of documents on the cloud.
d	The document which is processing under algorithm.
w	Word in d which is processing in the algorithm.
W_d	Weight of the word in d.
$F_{w,d}$	Number of word w in document d.
$F_{w,D}$	Number of word w in set of documents D.

Table 4 (Notations in algorithm)

1. Using functional API's in .Net framework, it provides the common pre-processing steps of document such as tokenization, stemming and removal of stop words.

2. The processed data is saved to the database for previously uploaded documents ‘**D**’.
3. Now when client is uploading a new document ‘**d**’, the document goes in a process state.

In the process state:

Firstly, API’s analysis the whole content in the document and do apply the above steps of tokenizing, stemming, removing of stop word then a separate database of fetched data is created. TFIDF algorithm is applied to that fetched data to gives the information of how much the words are important in the document and calculate the weight of the document (W_d).

TFIDF Algorithm

- i. Word **w** in the processing document **d** where $d \in D$.

Example:

w(d)	F_{w,d}	F_{w,D}
Every	6	106
Man	3	47
Die	7	2

Table 5

- ii. $W_d = f_{w,d} * \log(|d|/f_{w,D})$
- iii. Repeat above steps for all the words in **d** to calculate W_d for every word.
- iv. Words with high W_d imply that they are important words in **d**.

4. After the completion of the process state, the words with high W_d are compared to previously high W_d words in other $d \in D$.
5. When there are more than **X**% of the words matched with others, the document is marked as duplicate and pops up a message of duplicacy to the client.

The documents listed in table 1 is processed through Checker’s algorithm, it would not allow duplicate documents and data would look like as follows:

N O.	NAME	SIZE(KB)
1.	Security.pdf	253
2.	Networking.doc	1,208

3.	Pin_codes.pdf	452
5.	Design_issues.doc	2,183
5.	Information storage and management.txt	915

Table 6 (list of files on cloud after removing duplicacy)

Algorithm will not allow identical content on the cloud.

Enhancing the searching and accessing of documents from cloud:

In this paper, we also generate algorithm which deals with the classification of the cloud data. The classification in this algorithm is done on the basis of the **date** of data uploaded and the how much that data is **accessed** by the client. We will take the ratio of both vectors and generate a score which rates the document in the classification.

Brisk-Key/pronto-key Algorithm:

Variables	Description
SCORE	This determine the ranking of the file.
DAYS	Number of days the file is on the cloud.
CLICK	Number of times the file is accessed.
N	File which is processing for score calculation.
DISTANCE	Distance from Noida to server.

Table 7 (Notations of...)

1. Declare a variable **SCORE**.
2. Initialize the variable **DAYS** and returns the value of number of days the file on cloud.
3. Initialize the variable **CLICK** and returns the value of number of clicks or number of times the file is accessed.
4. Let say **Nth** document to calculate the score.
5. **CALCULATE_SCORE(DAYS, CLICK)** which is used to calculate the score by using this formula:

$$\text{SCORE(N)} = \text{CLICK(N)} / \text{DAYS(N)}$$

6. The above function will run until and calculates the score of **Nth** document and saves it to database.
7. Now, the documents are classified in an order using bubble sort algorithm so that the high

scored documents are on the top of the list and returns the list contains the top **k** documents for the client.

I D	File	Download	Days	Score
1	Data Classification Based on Confidentiality in Virtual Cloud Environment	452	20	22.6
2	Classification Of Big Point Cloud Data Using Cloud Computing	78	5	15.6
3	Classification of Cloud Data using Bayesian	130	9	14.444 44
4	Performance Enhancement of Classifiers using Integration of Clustering and Classification Techniques	632	45	14.044 44
5	Cloud Classification for Weather Information	150	13	11.538 46
6	Classification of Gene Expression Data on Public Clouds	89	8	11.125
7	k-Nearest Neighbor Classification over Semantically Secure Encrypted Cloud Data	521	54	9.6481 48
8	A Private Cloud Document Management System with Document Clustering Algorithm	69	8	8.625
9	Plagiarism Detection Based on SCAM Algorithm	745	98	7.6020 41
10	Big Data Classification Problems and Challenges	52	7	7.4285 71
11	3d security	40	6	6.6666 67
12	Web Document Clustering Approaches Using K-Means Algorithm	456	75	6.08
13	Implementation of Text clustering using Genetic	230	45	5.1111 11

Table 8 (Files classified by their scores)

Now the client have to select a document to proceed for the further steps of the algorithm. After the client selected a document.

8. The algorithm lists the number of servers on which the document is there.
9. Then it request client to give permission to detect the client's location.
10. After get access to client's location, it detects your location coordinates and server

coordinates and compare client’s geo-distance with the lists of servers on which the file resides.

DISTANCE=Mylocation.Location.DistanceTo(Server.Location)

11. The servers are arranged according to the nearest server from your location using bubble sorting algorithm.

The servers are sorted with their least distance from the client (28.5472°, 77.3366°).

I D	Server	Latitude	Longitud e	Distance from Noida(Km)
1	China	35.3789	104.3335	3096.395
2	Russia	66.1844	105.4268	5221.908
3	Korea	35.2743	127.6527	5644.406
4	Germany	52.1786	10.2694	7906.550
5	Algeria	28.1731	2.5908	8311.058
6	Australia	-25.837	130.2848	8439.540
7	Brazil	-9.019	-53.7216	15159.13
8	U.S	41.5811	-100.3329	19808.08
9	Mexico	24.5375	-102.364	19985.81
10	Canada	59.5369	-112.2685	21361.85

Table 9 (Servers listed with nearest distance)

12. When the client click the server to access the document, the client may not fully access the document, which will return ‘0’ and there is no change in the **CLICK(N)**.

13. When the client click the server to access the document and fully access the document, which will return ‘1’ and there is change in the **CLICK(N)** such that.

CLICK(N) =CLICK(N) + 1

14. If returns ‘1’, then goto **Step 5** to update Score in the database.

15. Else exit.

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

Clustering After completing the design of Roll Cage of ATV, its frame along with its material and cross section, the essential next step remains to test the rigidity and strength of the frame under severe conditions which is being done in ANSYS. As per the FEA Analysis it is to be find that the frame is able to withstand the impact, torsion, roll over conditions and provide utmost safety to the driver without undergoing much deformation.

Following tests were performed on the roll cage under the proposed FEA analysis:

- 1) Frontal impact test of Roll Cage
- 2) Wheel bump Dimension test
- 3) Longitudinal Torsion test for roll cage impact assessment

It is seen from the figure described above, the maximum stress value in the roll cage equals 1027.75KN/Sq. inch (1591.3 MPa) which seems to be exceeded to the safe value of 267.00KN/Sq. Inch. Hence modifications are needed to be made in the design. The Bracing members needed to be added in the chassis. Also some other members are added to the final roll cage frame to channelize the stress throughout the finite members of the roll cage design. Also the adequate positioning of its engines, gearbox component and suspension needs to be modified which is resulting in the applied changes to the roll cage system.

Results:

After the finalization of the desired ATV frame with the material and cross section of it, it is very essential to test the ATV's rigidity and the final strength of the frame under severe degradable conditions. As far as the design is concerned, the proposed roll cage is designed with a mere two box assembly which consist of the driver's cabin and the engine cabin. The steering system and its drum brake system which is integrated to the driver's cabin.

The ATV roll cage is designed so as to carry a driver of approximately 120kgs along with a fire extinguisher of 2kgs an engine of approximately 23kgs and a fine tuned gear box with differential arrangement of 16.5kgs. The beams which used are pipes with appropriate thickness. Pipe of circular some cross section which used, is get selected due to its availability in the local market and its relatively ability to withstand various forces.

Under the FEA analysis, there are following tests were performed on the designed roll cage

- (i) Front impact test
- (ii) Side impact test
- (iii) Rear impact test

Impact load calculation:

In FEA analysis,

With using the projected ATV vehicle without the driver mass of 455 kg,

The impact force was calculated based on a G-load of

$$4. F = ma =$$

$$455 \times 4 \times 10 = 18200 \text{ N}$$

The Impulse time = weight \times (velocity/load)

$$= 455 \times (16.67/18200) = 0.416 \text{ seconds}$$

We apply 18200 N from the front side for the test of the rear impact of the ATV roll cage structure of the proposed vehicle for finally determining the strength at the time of rear collision system.

Maximum deformation:

17.5010 mm Maximum deformation taken place for the rear impact done by simulation and it is also under the safe limit & not firmly get affects the safety of driver's cabin.

Maximum Von Mises Stress counted = 156.860 MPa

The Incorporated Factor of Safety = σ_y / σ_{max}

$$= 355.00/156.860$$

$$= 2.260$$

As with the results of this FEA analysis, the factor of Safety for automobiles goes up to 8 points, hence the design is pretty good safer against the specified stress previously tested.

The Side impact analysis

The Impact load calculation is performed using the projected ATV vehicle/driver mass of 455 kgs,

the impact force was get calculated on the basis of a G-load of approximately 2.

Than

$$F = ma = 455 \times 2 \times 10 = 9100 \text{ N}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{The Impulse time} &= \text{total weight} \times (\text{velocity of vehicle} / \text{pay load}) \\ &= 455 \times (16.67/9100) = 0.8335 \text{ seconds}\end{aligned}$$

We had applied upto 9100 Newton force from the side for the test of side impact of the designed ATV roll cage structure of the vehicle for determining strength at the time of the particular side collision.

And after the FEA and roll cage simulation and calculation based result analysis we find that the Maximum VonMises Stress = 184.710 MPa

$$\begin{aligned}\text{With Incorporated Factor of Safety} &= \sigma_{yt} / \sigma_{\max} \\ &= 355.0/184.710 = 1.920\end{aligned}$$

As the final factor of Safety for ATV based automobiles goes up to 8points, hence design is considered safe and secure against specified stress and the designed roll cage is also selected for the fabrication.

V. CONCLUSION:

The FEA analysis of an ATV, in this study, demonstrated the structural superiority of the proposed roll cage design while maintaining a lower weight to strength ratio in proper manner. The customers' utmost needs were remain taken the top most priority because they are remain the ultimate goal of every automobile manufacturer.

The ATV vehicle design, in this FEA analysis demonstrated the desired satisfactory dynamic stability while maneuvering rough terrains in simulation. The proposed design of the ATV vehicle is kept very simple keeping in view its manufacturability and other desired specifications. Thus at this point of time our ATV design can be barely redacted to heading in correct direction. There is a lot of future work which is much essentially required to fine tune the overall performance of ATV in real situations. The design analysis, its development and fabrication now can be carried out based on the FEA results with great success. The designed roll cage is than used to build an ATV by integrating most of all other automotive systems like the transmission, adequate suspension, adequate type of steering, hydraulic brakes and the other miscellaneous elements.

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